

**THE EFFECT OF SCHOOL PRINCIPAL LEADERSHIP, CURRICULUM
MANAGEMENT, AND TEACHER PROFESSIONALISM ON THE QUALITY OF
HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATION IN DEPOK CITY**

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Abstract

Education is carried out so that students have control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills. During online learning, the quality of education has decreased. This study was conducted to analyze the influence of principals' leadership, management, the influence of teacher professionalism on the quality of public high school education in Depok City and the simultaneous influence of principals' leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism on the quality of public high school education in Depok City. The study was also conducted to determine the most dominant influence on the quality of public high school education in Depok City. The population in this study were all 593 public high school teachers in Depok City with a total sample of 221. The data used in this study were primary data and secondary data. The primary data collection used is a questionnaire, while the secondary data collected is obtained through the documentation/archives available on the website of the Education Office. Analysis of research data using multiple linear regression. Based on the results of the study, the leadership of the principal affects the quality of education in Public Senior High Schools in Depok City, curriculum management affects the quality of education in Public Senior High Schools in Depok City, teacher professionalism affects the education quality of State Senior High Schools in Depok City. Simultaneously, the principal's leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism have an effect on the education quality of State Senior High Schools in Depok City and curriculum management has the most dominant influence on the quality of education.

Keywords: Leadership, Management, Quality, Professionalism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is important in building human resources. According to Rohma, Harapan, and Wardiah (2020), education is carried out so that students have control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills. Thus, people who want to achieve maximum self-quality consciously and planned will create a learning atmosphere and an active learning process. Education can be carried out in a democratic and fair manner and is not discriminatory.

In the implementation of activities in the field of education, it is necessary to have subjects who are the implementers of development, namely educators and education staff. According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 20 (2003), educators are educational staff who have qualifications according to their specificity, and participate in providing education. The teaching staff consists of teachers, lecturers, counselors, tutors, widyasarana, tutors, instructors, facilitators, and other names. Meanwhile, education staff according to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 20 (2003) are community members who are dedicated to being appointed to support the implementation of education.

The quality of education to be achieved by the Indonesian people in the future is the ability to compete with other nations, especially in the era of increasingly rapid technological development. These human qualities can be achieved through the implementation of quality education. Therefore, educators and education personnel who have a very important role need to meet educational standards. The Deputy Secretary General of the Federation of Indonesian Teachers' Unions (FSGI) said that problems in the online learning process have caused a decline in the quality of education in Indonesia (CNN Indonesia 2020). This needs to be a concern to study further what causes the decline in the quality of education during online learning activities. Based on research conducted by Akmal and Santaria (2020), during online learning during the Covid 19 pandemic, the quality of education decreased and faced many challenges. This happens because during online learning students find it difficult to understand the learning material. Akmal and Santaria (2020) also explained that the character of students has decreased in quality due to online learning because the role of the teacher cannot be replaced with any sophisticated machines or technology.

Some researchers explain that there are several factors that affect the quality of education. Research from Sari (2013) explains that the principal's leadership and teacher achievement motivation affect the quality of education. Another study was conducted by Suhartini, Milfayetty, and Rahman (2021) which explained that the principal's academic

supervision and teacher professionalism affect the quality of education. Different from Suwartini's research, research from Syuaibah, Qowaid, and Norman (2020), explains that curriculum management and teacher professionalism affect the quality of education. Based on several studies on the factors that affect the quality of education, three variables were selected, namely principal leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism. Sari (2013) explains that in order to achieve quality output, human resources (HR) are needed.

Principal leadership comes from two words, namely leadership and principal. According to Kosim (2017), leadership is a process or ability to influence others. An important element in leadership is that there are other people who are influenced and there are certain goals to be achieved. Meanwhile, Idris (2018), explains that leadership also means the art of influencing others to cooperate to achieve goals. Based on the explanation above, leadership means efforts to influence others to achieve a goal. Tara and Novitria (2020) explained that the millennial generation is a generation that has the ability to utilize or use information and communication technology so that online media becomes their need.

Curriculum management according to Zamakhsyari, Suhendri, and Lubis (2019) is a combination of two words, namely management and curriculum. Management is an activity or process that involves or utilizes all available resources to achieve effective and efficient organizational goals. Meanwhile, curriculum means a plan of teaching or education programs provided to students for educational purposes. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that curriculum management means activities carried out so that teaching programs in education can run effectively and efficiently. Nasbi (2017) explains that in curriculum management there are five principles that must be considered. Curriculum management according to Syuaibah, Qowaid, and Norman (2020) can also be interpreted as a process to improve the quality of education by utilizing existing resources through a series of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling.

According to Khotimah (2020), teacher professionalism is the ability of teachers to carry out their main duties as educators and teachers including the ability to plan, conduct, and carry out learning evaluations. Syuaibah, et al (2020) explained that professional teachers are teachers who have the competence and expertise and are responsible for realizing quality education. Based on the explanation above, professionalism means the ability of teachers to realize quality education in a responsible manner to achieve educational goals.

According to Susanto and Mattalata (2018), quality is a measure to state the essence of something, both objects and others, based on the ideal standards to be achieved by a process. Timor, Saud, and Suhardan (2018) explain that education quality indicators are influenced by customer focus, leadership, involvement of people, process approach, system approach to management, continuous improvement, factual approach to decision making, mutual benefit supplier benefit relationship. Nationally, the education quality standard refers to the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 13 of 2015 concerning the Second Amendment to Government Regulation no. 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards (Regulation of the Government of the Republic of Indonesia 2015).

Teachers as school human resources are required to carry out their responsibilities professionally, while to carry out these responsibilities properly, it is very dependent on the leadership style of the principal. Principals need to do several things as a strategy to maintain the quality of education, for example by conducting monthly coaching to monitor the performance of school management, teachers, and school employees. Coaching is carried out so that all parties involved in learning activities can evaluate each other's performance and can make improvements if needed. In addition to teachers and principals, curriculum management as planners and implementers of the learning process must have a strategy so that learning activities can run effectively and are adapted to the needs of students so that curriculum goals can be achieved.

2. METHODOLOGY AND TECHNIQUES USED

This research is a quantitative method. According to Sugiyono (2013:37) quantitative research is carried out by testing hypotheses or solving problems on the basis of theoretical deduction using statistical data measurements. The population of this study were all public high school teachers in the city of Depok. An overview of the study population can be seen in Table 2. 1.

Table 2.1. Number of State Senior High School Teachers in Depok

No	Name of School	Gender		Total Teacher
		Male	Female	
1.	SMA Negeri 1 Depok	19	31	50 People
2.	SMA Negeri 2 Depok	9	33	42 People
3.	SMA Negeri 3 Depok	14	41	55 People

No	Name of School	Gender		Total Teacher
		Male	Female	
4.	SMA Negeri 4 Depok	17	35	52 People
5.	SMA Negeri 5 Depok	21	26	47 People
6.	SMA Negeri 6 Depok	15	33	48 People
7.	SMA Negeri 7 Depok	11	26	37 People
8.	SMA Negeri 8 Depok	17	28	45 People
9.	SMA Negeri 9 Depok	15	22	37 People
10.	SMA Negeri 10 Depok	26	36	62 People
11.	SMA Negeri 11 Depok	19	12	31 People
12.	SMA Negeri 12 Depok	9	18	27 People
13.	SMA Negeri 13 Depok	15	33	48 People
14.	SMA Negeri 14 Depok	6	6	12 People
Total Population		213	380	593 People

Source: <https://sekolahdata.kemendikbud.go.id/>

The sample in this study was determined using a table developed by Issac and Michael in Sugiyono's book (2011:87) so that the sample There were 221 studies with a significance level of 5%. The sampling technique used is incidental sampling, which is a sampling technique that is accidental or incidental so that anyone who meets the researcher and is suitable as a data source can be used for research samples.

The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. The primary data used in this study used a questionnaire. In addition to primary data, this study uses secondary data. Secondary data is data that is collected or obtained through documentation/archives available on the website of the Education Office to support primary data. The research question indicators for the variables of principal leadership (X1), curriculum management (X2), teacher professionalism (X3), and quality of education (Y) are described in table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Research Indicators

Variable	Indicator	Number of Question
Principal Leadership Questions (X1)	Determine goals, implementation of reality work.	1
	Equip employees with the necessary sources of funds to carry out their	2

Variable	Indicator	Number of Question
	duties.	
	Communicating commensurate rewards to encourage achievement.	3
	Delegate authority when necessary and invite participation when necessary.	4
	Remove barriers to effective work execution.	5
	Assess the performance of the work and communicate the results.	6
	Shows concern for subordinates.	7
Curriculum Management (X2)	Planning learning opportunities for students so that they can make changes for the better.	8
	Planning learning opportunities for teachers so that they can make changes for the better.	9
	Designing curriculum materials with the aim of making it easier for students to learn learning materials.	10
	Implementation of the curriculum is realized in the teaching and learning process in accordance with the principles and demands of the curriculum.	11
	Curriculum evaluation is a measurement or decision-making process about the value of an object.	12
Teacher Professionalism (X3)	Pedagogic	15
	Personal	16-17

Variable	Indicator	Number of Question
Quality of education (Y)	Social	18-19
	Professional competence	20-21
	Graduate competency	22
	Content	23
	Process standard	24
	Standards of educators and education personnel	25
	Standards of management	26
	Standards of financing	27
	Standards of assessment	28

This study used the primary data, namely power that is directly obtained from research respondents through a closed questionnaire of 28 items. The questionnaire was calculated using a Likert scale in the form of a checklist and scores on the answers of research subjects based on the following conditions:

4 = always

3 = often

2 = sometimes

1 = never

3. CASE STUDY

Leadership is an effort to influence others to achieve goals. Based on this explanation, the principal's leadership means the ability or effort of the principal in influencing others in achieving school goals. The principal's leadership behavior will have an impact on working conditions. According to Susanto and Mattalata (2018) the policies taken by the principal will have an influence on the performance of teachers and school employees so that it will affect the quality of education. This shows that the better the leadership of the principal, the better the quality of education in schools.

Curriculum management means activities carried out so that teaching programs in education can run effectively and efficiently. According to Sista (2017) curriculum management affects the quality of education through new innovations in learning models. Curriculum management must be able to ensure that teaching and educational activities in

schools achieve the target of quality education. The better the curriculum management in schools, the better the quality of education, so that curriculum management affects the quality of education.

Teachers as educators have National Standards so that educational goals can be achieved. These standards show that educators do their jobs professionally. According to Dewi and Khotimah (2020), professionalism affects the quality of education. Teacher professionalism is the ability of a teacher in carrying out his main duties as an educator through teaching and educational activities starting from the planning, implementation, to evaluation of students in accordance with educational targets or achievements. This shows that teacher professionalism affects the quality of education because teachers who carry out their main tasks well and professionally will improve the quality of education in schools.

Based on the above framework, a research model was created because the principal's leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism affect the quality of education. The research model is presented in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. The Model of Research

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine whether the existing hypothesis has a positive or negative contribution. Through the existing hypotheses, it is determined which one has the greatest influence on the quality of education in State Senior High Schools in Depok City. Based on the results of the questionnaire filled in by 221 respondents, the demographics of respondents are presented in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Number of Respondents

Gender	Total Respondents	Percentage
Male	72	28%

Female	149	72%
TOTAL	221	100%

The data shows that male respondents are 72 with a percentage of 28% and female respondents are 149 with a percentage of 72% so that respondents are more many are of the female gender. Analysis of the data description will describe the respondents' answers to the questions posed in each variable. The results of the coefficient of determination test are used to determine how much the independent variable explains the dependent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination test are presented in table 4.2.

Based on table 4.2 it is known that the Adjusted R² value of 0.205 means 20.5% variation in Education Quality can be explained by variations of three independent variables (leadership leadership, curriculum management, and quality of education).). While the rest (100-20.5 = 79.5%) is explained by other reasons outside the model. Standard Error of the Estimate 1.51303, the smaller the SEE value, the more accurate the regression model predicts the dependent variable.

The F test is used to prove that there is a significant influence between the variables of principal leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism on the quality of education. The results of the F test are presented in table 4.3.

Table 4.3. F test

Model Summary				
R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
.464 ^a	.215	.205		1.51303
a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Education				
b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher Professionalism, Principal Leadership, Curriculum Management				

Based on table 6 it is known that the calculated F value is 19.869 with probability <0.001. The probability value is smaller than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the three variables (leadership leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism) simultaneously affect the quality of education.

T test was used to determine whether each independent variable (leadership leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism) significantly affected the dependent variable (quality of education). The way to determine the effect of each variable is

significant or not, the method used is to look at the significance value. T test results are presented in table 4.4.

Table 4.4. Test T

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.095	2.021		4.995	<.001
	Principal Leadership	.137	.068	.128	2.019	.045
	Curriculum Management	.252	.064	.261	3.961	<.001
	Teacher Professionalism	.203	.059	.229	3.414	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Quality of Education

Based on table 4.4. explained that:

- 1) Based on the significance value (Sig.) of the X1 variable the principal's leadership was 0.045. Because the value of Sig. 0.045 < 0.05, it can be concluded that the principal's leadership has an effect on the quality of education.
- 2) Based on the significance value (Sig.) of the curriculum management variable X2 of < 0.001. Because the value of Sig. 0.001 < 0.05, it can be concluded that curriculum management has an effect on the quality of education.
- 3) Based on the significance value (Sig.) of the X3 variable, teacher professionalism is < 0.001. Because the value of Sig. 0.001 < 0.05, it can be concluded that teacher professionalism affects the quality of education.
- 4) Based on the Standardized Coefficients Beta of the principal's leadership of (0.128), curriculum management of (0.261), and teacher professionalism of (0.229) so that the variable that affects the quality of education is curriculum management.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research on the principal's leadership variable, it positively and significantly affects the education quality of State Senior High Schools in Depok City, which means that the better the principal's leadership, the higher the education quality of State Senior High Schools in Depok City. Based on the results of research on the curriculum management variable has the most dominant value which has a positive and significant effect on the education quality of State Senior High Schools in Depok City. If the curriculum management is better, the higher the quality of education for public high schools in Depok City. Based on the results of research on the variable of teacher professionalism positively and significantly influences the quality of education in State Senior High Schools in Depok City. The better the professionalism of the teacher, the higher the education quality of the State Senior High School in Depok City. Based on the results of research on curriculum management variables positively and significantly affect the quality of education in State High Schools in Depok City.

The results of this thesis research can be used as information for schools in improving the quality of education. Schools that want good quality education can consider how the principal's leadership is applied, how curriculum management designs, implements, and evaluates learning activities and how the professionalism of educators or teachers in schools. The conclusions of this study can be used as information for both schools and the government and the community to jointly determine the influence of school principal leadership, curriculum management, and teacher professionalism on the quality of education so that it can be useful in making decisions to maximize the quality of education in Indonesia.

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